

Illuminating the Future of Medicine: Surface Plasmon Resonance-Based Nanotechnologies for Genetic Disorder Management

Shashikant, Meghna Singh, Faith Ruth Dixon, Aniruddha Basak, Mahammad Ayaan, Arnab Roy

Kalinga University, Kotni, Atal Nagar-Nava Raipur, Chhattisgarh 492101

ABSTRACT

Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR)-based nanotechnologies are emerging as a groundbreaking paradigm in molecular medicine, particularly in the comprehensive management of genetic disorders. These sophisticated technological platforms leverage the unique optical properties of metallic interfaces to enable ultra-sensitive detection of biomolecular interactions with remarkable precision and real-time capability. By exploiting nanoscale electromagnetic wave phenomena at metal-dielectric interfaces, SPR nanotechnologies facilitate instantaneous molecular characterization, enabling researchers and clinicians to probe intricate genetic mechanisms with unprecedented resolution. The transformative potential of these nanotechnological approaches lies in their ability to bridge sophisticated molecular detection with targeted therapeutic interventions. Through advanced sensor configurations and nanomaterial engineering, SPR platforms can rapidly identify subtle genetic variations, quantify protein-protein interactions, and map complex molecular signaling pathways associated with inherited diseases. This technological convergence offers promising strategies for early diagnosis, personalized treatment monitoring, and potentially developing innovative genetic therapeutic modalities. By integrating cutting-edge nanoscience with molecular diagnostics, SPR-based technologies are poised to revolutionize our understanding and management of genetic disorders, representing a significant leap forward in personalized medical interventions.

Keywords: Surface Plasmon Resonance, Nanotechnology, Genetic Disorders, Molecular Detection, Precision Medicine, Biomolecular Interactions.

INTRODUCTION

Surface Plasmon Resonance Nanotechnology

Fundamental Principles

Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) represents a sophisticated electromagnetic phenomenon manifesting at the critical interface between metallic substrates and dielectric environments, predominantly characterized by electron dynamics and quantum interactions. The intricate optical mechanism emerges when electromagnetic radiation specifically polarized light—impinges upon metallic surfaces constructed from noble metals such as gold or silver, typically featuring nanoscale architectural configurations. During this sophisticated interaction, conduction electrons within the metallic lattice collectively oscillate in coherent resonance, generating localized electromagnetic field perturbations that exhibit profound sensitivity to minute environmental alterations. These quantum-level electron oscillations,

termed surface plasmons, propagate along the metal-dielectric boundary, creating an evanescent wave characterized by exponential decay perpendicular to the interface. The resonance condition is meticulously governed by complex electromagnetic boundary conditions, quantum mechanical principles and precise angular and wavelength parameters [1-5].

Sophisticated optical detection methodologies enable researchers to quantify these electron plasma oscillations with exceptional precision, transforming SPR into a powerful analytical technique across multiple scientific domains. The phenomenon's remarkable sensitivity arises from the profound electromagnetic coupling between incident light and free electron dynamics, allowing detection of molecular interactions, surface adsorption processes, and nanoscale structural modifications with unprecedented resolution. In biochemical and biosensing applications, SPR enables real-time

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

monitoring of biomolecular interactions, facilitating investigations into protein-ligand binding kinetics, receptor-substrate engagements, and complex molecular recognition mechanisms. Materials science leverages SPR for characterizing surface chemistry, examining nanomaterial interfaces, and exploring quantum electromagnetic interactions at unprecedented spatial and temporal scales. Physicists and engineers exploit this phenomenon through sophisticated experimental configurations, utilizing prism-based Kretschmann geometries or advanced nanophotonic platforms that manipulate electromagnetic wave propagation. The resonance condition emerges when the wave vector of incident photons precisely matches the surface plasmon wave vector, creating a unique quantum mechanical coupling that enables energy transfer and information extraction. Contemporary research continues to explore SPR's fundamental mechanisms, developing increasingly sophisticated theoretical models and experimental techniques that bridge quantum electrodynamics, materials science, and nanoscale sensing technologies. By comprehensively understanding and manipulating these electron plasma oscillations, researchers can design innovative sensing platforms, advanced optical metamaterials, and quantum-enhanced diagnostic technologies with transformative potential across scientific and technological landscapes [6-10].

Fig. 1. Schematic Experimental Setup for Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) Excitation

In the experimental arrangement for SPR excitation, a sensor chip coated with a thin layer of gold is positioned on a prism or hemispherical base. A polarized light beam, originating from a light source (indicated by a star), is directed onto the sensor chip. The intensity of the light reflected from the chip's surface is captured and measured by a detector (represented by a disk). When the light reaches a specific angle of incidence (denoted as ϕ), surface

plasmons are excited at the gold film's interface. This excitation leads to a noticeable dip in the intensity of the reflected light, marked as point A. Any variation in the refractive index at the gold film's surface alters the resonance condition, causing a shift in the angle of minimum reflection from A to B. This shift forms the basis for detecting molecular interactions and changes in the surrounding medium.

1.1. Nanoscale Sensing Mechanisms

Nanoscale sensing mechanisms, particularly those utilizing Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR), represent a sophisticated paradigm in molecular detection and biomolecular interaction analysis. These advanced nanosensing platforms exploit the intricate electromagnetic interactions occurring at metal-dielectric interfaces, enabling unprecedented sensitivity in molecular detection. The fundamental principle underlying SPR-based nanosensors involves the resonant oscillation of free electrons at metallic surfaces when excited by specific wavelengths of electromagnetic radiation. This phenomenon allows for extraordinarily precise measurements of molecular binding events, surface adsorption, and conformational changes at the nanoscale. The core technological innovation of SPR nanosensors lies in their ability to transduce molecular interactions into measurable optical signals with remarkable resolution. By leveraging thin metallic films, typically composed of gold or silver, these sensors can detect minute changes in the local refractive index with exceptional precision. When biomolecules interact with the sensor surface, they induce localized perturbations in the electron plasma oscillations, which manifest as distinct shifts in the resonance angle or wavelength. This intrinsic sensitivity enables the detection of molecular interactions in the picomolar to femtomolar range, surpassing traditional analytical methodologies. Genetic material and protein interaction quantification represent critical domains where SPR nanosensors demonstrate transformative capabilities. The label-free nature of these sensing mechanisms eliminates the requirement for fluorescent markers or radioactive tags, thereby minimizing potential interference and preserving the native molecular environment. By monitoring real-time binding kinetics with millisecond temporal resolution, researchers can elucidate complex biomolecular interactions, characterize binding affinities, and assess molecular recognition processes

with unprecedented granularity. The versatility of SPR nanosensors extends across multiple scientific disciplines, including medical diagnostics, pharmaceutical research, environmental monitoring, and biotechnology. Their capacity to operate in complex biological matrices, coupled with minimal sample preparation requirements, renders them particularly advantageous for rapid, sensitive molecular analysis. Furthermore, the integration of nanoscale sensing mechanisms with microfluidic technologies and advanced computational algorithms enables sophisticated data acquisition and interpretation strategies. Technological advancements in nanofabrication and surface chemistry have significantly enhanced the performance of SPR nanosensors. Innovative surface modifications, such as functionalized self-assembled monolayers and biomimetic coatings, enable selective molecular capturing and minimize non-specific interactions. These strategic enhancements improve sensor specificity, extend operational stability, and broaden the range of detectable molecular species.

The scientific significance of SPR-based nanoscale sensing mechanisms lies not only in their extraordinary sensitivity but also in their potential to revolutionize molecular diagnostics and research. By providing real-time, quantitative insights into molecular interactions at unprecedented spatial and temporal scales, these nanosensors bridge critical knowledge gaps across biological, chemical, and medical sciences. The continuous refinement of SPR technologies promises increasingly sophisticated analytical capabilities, potentially transforming our understanding of complex molecular systems and enabling more precise, personalized approaches to diagnostics and therapeutic interventions. The interdisciplinary nature of nanoscale sensing underscores the convergence of physics, chemistry, biology, and engineering. As researchers continue to explore and optimize SPR nanosensing platforms, they are progressively expanding the boundaries of molecular detection, offering profound implications for fundamental scientific research and translational applications across diverse domains of human knowledge and technological innovation [11-13].

Fig. 2. Sensogram

This graph illustrates the relationship between the angle of the dip and time. Initially, the sensor surface remains unchanged, establishing a baseline with the dip observed at the SPR angle (Point A). Following the injection of the sample (indicated by an arrow), biomolecules interact with the sensor surface, leading to adsorption. This interaction alters the refractive index, causing a shift in the SPR angle to a new position (Point B), representing the association phase. The dynamic process of adsorption and desorption can be monitored in real time, enabling quantification of the adsorbed molecules. When the analyte-ligand complex dissociates, replacing the sample with system buffer facilitates the desorption phase.

2. Diagnostic Applications in Genetic Disorders

2.1. Early Detection Strategies

SPR nanotechnologies offer revolutionary approaches to genetic disorder diagnostics:

- **Mutation Detection**

The landscape of genetic disorder diagnostics has been dramatically transformed by surface plasmon resonance (SPR) nanotechnologies, which represent a paradigm shift in ultrasensitive molecular detection methodologies. These advanced nanoscale platforms enable unprecedented precision in identifying genetic mutations through sophisticated molecular recognition mechanisms. At the core of SPR nanotechnological approaches lies an extraordinary capability to detect single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) with remarkable sensitivity, fundamentally revolutionizing our understanding of genetic variation detection.

The technological prowess of SPR nanotechnologies manifests in their ability to screen genetic variations with extraordinary resolution, capable of identifying mutations at extraordinarily low concentrations as minimal as 10^{-12} molecular concentrations. This unprecedented sensitivity represents a quantum leap

in genetic diagnostic capabilities, allowing researchers and clinicians to detect subtle genetic alterations that might previously have gone unnoticed. The intrinsic power of these nanotechnological platforms stems from their sophisticated optical sensing mechanisms, which leverage localized surface plasmon resonance phenomena to generate highly precise molecular interaction measurements. Genetic mutation detection through SPR nanotechnologies transcends traditional diagnostic limitations by providing rapid, comprehensive screening methodologies. The technology's inherent strengths include its capacity to simultaneously analyze multiple genetic markers, offering a holistic approach to understanding genetic variations associated with inherited disorders. By employing sophisticated nanoscale sensor arrays and advanced signal transduction techniques, SPR platforms can rapidly interrogate genetic sequences with unprecedented accuracy and speed.

The molecular recognition strategies embedded within these nanotechnological systems exploit intricate biomolecular interactions, utilizing specialized receptor molecules designed to selectively bind and identify specific genetic sequences. These receptors are engineered with extraordinary precision, enabling them to distinguish between wildtype and mutated genetic fragments with near-absolute specificity. The resultant diagnostic approach allows for comprehensive genetic profiling that can potentially predict disease susceptibility, understand genetic predispositions, and guide personalized medical interventions.

Moreover, SPR nanotechnologies offer significant advantages in terms of minimal sample requirements and rapid analysis times. The ability to detect genetic mutations at extremely low concentrations means that even minute biological samples can yield comprehensive genetic insights. This characteristic is particularly revolutionary in fields such as prenatal screening, oncological research, and personalized medicine, where early and precise genetic information can be transformative in clinical decision-making processes.

The scientific significance of these nanotechnological platforms extends beyond mere detection, representing a fundamental reimagining of molecular diagnostic paradigms. By bridging nanoscale engineering, optical physics, and molecular biology,

SPR technologies are poised to revolutionize our approach to understanding genetic complexity, offering unprecedented insights into the intricate molecular mechanisms underlying genetic disorders [14-18].

• Genetic Screening Platforms

The landscape of genetic disorder diagnostics has undergone a transformative evolution through the integration of Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) nanotechnologies, presenting a paradigm shift in molecular detection methodologies. These advanced platforms represent a sophisticated approach to genetic screening, leveraging nanoscale engineering to dramatically enhance diagnostic precision and efficiency. The fundamental principle underlying SPR nanotechnologies involves the intricate manipulation of electromagnetic interactions at metal-dielectric interfaces, enabling unprecedented sensitivity in genetic marker detection. Contemporary SPR-based genetic screening platforms demonstrate remarkable capabilities in simultaneous multiparametric analysis, allowing for the comprehensive evaluation of multiple genetic markers within a single experimental framework. This multiplexed detection strategy represents a significant departure from traditional single-marker diagnostic approaches, providing researchers and clinicians with a holistic perspective on genetic variations. The technological innovation inherent in these platforms substantially reduces the requisite sample volume, addressing critical limitations in previous diagnostic methodologies and minimizing invasive sampling procedures [19, 20].

The temporal efficiency of SPR nanotechnologies is particularly noteworthy, with analysis times compressed dramatically compared to conventional genetic screening techniques. Where traditional methods might require extended periods for comprehensive genetic marker assessment, these nanotechnology-enabled platforms can generate comprehensive molecular profiles in remarkably condensed timeframes. This acceleration of diagnostic processes not only enhances clinical workflow efficiency but also enables more rapid interventional strategies in genetic disorder management [21].

The molecular sensitivity of SPR nanotechnologies is predicated on sophisticated nanoscale sensor architectures that can detect minute genetic variations

with unprecedented precision. These platforms exploit sophisticated optical and electromagnetic principles to transduce molecular interactions into quantifiable signals, allowing for the detection of genetic markers at exceptionally low concentration ranges. The nanoscale engineering underlying these technologies enables the identification of subtle genetic modifications that might escape detection through conventional diagnostic methodologies. Critically, the multiplexed detection capabilities of SPR nanotechnologies transcend traditional diagnostic limitations by simultaneously interrogating multiple genetic markers within a single experimental construct. This comprehensive approach provides a more nuanced and holistic understanding of genetic complexity, enabling researchers to map intricate genetic interactions and potential disorder predispositions with remarkable depth and accuracy. The technological infrastructure supporting these platforms integrates advanced nanomaterials, sophisticated optical detection mechanisms, and computational algorithms to generate comprehensive genetic profiles. The transformative potential of SPR nanotechnologies extends beyond mere diagnostic capabilities, representing a fundamental reimagining of genetic screening paradigms. By dramatically reducing sample volume requirements, minimizing analysis time, and providing unprecedented molecular detection sensitivity, these platforms promise to revolutionize our approach to genetic disorder diagnostics. The convergence of nanotechnology, molecular biology, and advanced optical sensing represents a critical milestone in personalized medicine, offering unprecedented insights into genetic complexity and potential therapeutic interventions [22, 23].

2.2. Key Diagnostic Techniques

• Surface Plasmon Resonance-Enabled DNA Hybridization Detection

Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR)-based DNA hybridization detection represents a sophisticated molecular diagnostic approach that leverages advanced nanotechnology for precise genetic sequence analysis. This innovative technique fundamentally transforms genetic diagnostic methodologies by integrating functionalized gold nanoparticles as critical sensing platforms. The methodology capitalizes on the unique optical and electromagnetic properties of gold nanoparticles,

which demonstrate exceptional sensitivity in detecting molecular interactions at nanoscale resolution.

The underlying mechanism of SPR-based detection involves strategically engineered gold nanoparticles functionalized with specific molecular probes designed to recognize target genetic sequences. When complementary DNA or RNA strands interact with these functionalized nanoparticles, distinctive changes occur in the surface plasmon resonance spectrum, generating measurable optical signals. These signals provide instantaneous and highly specific information about genetic sequence interactions, enabling researchers and clinicians to identify genetic variations, mutations, or pathogenic markers with unprecedented accuracy. The technological sophistication of this approach lies in its ability to directly visualize molecular interactions with near-instantaneous results. By manipulating the physicochemical properties of gold nanoparticles, researchers can modulate the sensitivity and specificity of the detection process. The functionalization strategies involve precise chemical modifications that enhance the nanoparticles' binding capabilities, allowing them to selectively recognize and capture target genetic sequences with remarkable precision.

Critically, SPR-based DNA hybridization detection offers several significant advantages over traditional genetic diagnostic techniques. The methodology eliminates complex, time-consuming sample preparation protocols and provides real-time molecular interaction monitoring. The high specificity of the technique minimizes potential false-positive or false-negative results, which are common challenges in genetic diagnostics. Furthermore, the approach requires minimal sample volumes, making it particularly valuable in scenarios with limited genetic material.

The versatility of this technique extends across multiple scientific domains, including clinical diagnostics, genetic research, pathogen identification, and personalized medicine. Researchers can adapt the gold nanoparticle probes to target specific genetic sequences associated with various conditions, from infectious diseases to inherited genetic disorders. The rapid detection capabilities and high-resolution molecular interaction visualization make this method particularly promising for developing advanced

diagnostic platforms. Technological innovations continue to refine SPR-based DNA hybridization detection, with ongoing research focusing on enhancing nanoparticle design, improving signal-to-noise ratios, and developing more sophisticated computational algorithms for data interpretation. As nanotechnology and molecular diagnostics converge, possibilities for molecular diagnostics, genetic research, and personalized healthcare interventions [24-27].

• **Nanoprobe Technologies**

Contemporary diagnostic methodologies have witnessed remarkable advancements through sophisticated nanoprobe technologies, representing a paradigm shift in molecular detection strategies. These innovative diagnostic platforms leverage functionalized nanoparticles engineered with remarkable precision to target specific genetic sequences with unprecedented accuracy. The fundamental mechanism involves strategically designed nanoparticles that can interact selectively with target molecular markers, enabling unprecedented resolution in genetic and cellular analysis. By incorporating advanced surface modifications, these nanoparticles demonstrate extraordinary capabilities in navigating complex biological environments, achieving enhanced signal amplification through intricate molecular engineering techniques. The core scientific principle underlying nanoprobe technologies centers on their ability to amplify molecular signals with exceptional sensitivity, particularly in scenarios involving rare mutation detection. This amplification mechanism is achieved through sophisticated surface chemistry and quantum-scale interactions that allow nanoparticles to generate substantial signal enhancement even when confronted with minimal genetic variations. Researchers have developed specialized disease diagnostics, and personalized medicine. By enabling detection of rare genetic mutations with extraordinary sensitivity, these technologies represent a pivotal advancement in molecular diagnostic capabilities, bridging the gap between molecular-level understanding and comprehensive clinical interpretation. The continuous evolution of nanoprobe technologies underscores the dynamic nature of modern diagnostic approaches, highlighting the ongoing convergence of nanotechnology, molecular

this technique represents a pivotal advancement in understanding and analyzing complex genetic interactions with unprecedented precision and efficiency. The scientific potential of SPR-based DNA hybridization detection remains substantial, offering transformative

functionalization strategies that enable nanoparticles to recognize and bind to specific genetic sequences with remarkable selectivity, effectively transforming molecular diagnostics from traditional bulk analysis to high-precision, single-molecule detection platforms.

Technological innovations in nanoprobe design have significantly expanded the boundaries of diagnostic sensitivity. By implementing advanced functionalization protocols, these nanoparticles can be tailored to recognize intricate molecular signatures with near-perfect specificity. The enhanced signal amplification capabilities enable detection of genetic mutations that would have remained unidentifiable through conventional diagnostic methodologies, representing a critical breakthrough in precision medicine and molecular pathology.

The multidimensional approach of nanoprobe technologies encompasses several sophisticated strategies, including surface chemistry optimization, quantum dot integration, and advanced molecular targeting mechanisms. These nanoparticles are meticulously engineered to navigate complex biological microenvironments, interact with specific genetic sequences, and generate amplified signals that provide researchers and clinicians with unprecedented insights into molecular-level diagnostic information. The transformative potential of these nanoprobe technologies extends across multiple scientific domains, including oncological research, genetic screening, infectious

biology, and advanced computational methodologies. As research progresses, these sophisticated diagnostic platforms are expected to revolutionize our understanding of genetic variations, disease mechanisms, and personalized therapeutic interventions, ultimately enhancing our capacity to comprehend and address complex molecular pathologies with unprecedented precision and insight [28-30].

Table 1. **Diagnostic Applications of SPR Nanotechnologies in Genetic Disorders**

Application	Description	Advantages	Examples
Mutation Detection	Utilizes SPR platforms for identifying genetic mutations with ultrasensitivity, including SNP detection.	High sensitivity (as low as 10^{-12} concentrations), minimal sample requirement, rapid analysis.	Prenatal screening, oncology.
Genetic Screening Platforms	Multiparametric analysis of multiple genetic markers using advanced SPR systems.	Simultaneous marker detection, reduced sample volume, rapid diagnosis, improved clinical workflow.	Inherited disorders screening.
DNA Hybridization Detection	SPR-based platforms employing functionalized gold nanoparticles for precise genetic sequence analysis.	Real-time monitoring, high specificity, minimal preparation, rapid and accurate results.	Pathogen identification.
Nanoprobe Technologies	Functionalized nanoparticles engineered for specific molecular targeting, enhancing sensitivity and precision in diagnostics.	Rare mutation detection, signal amplification, single-molecule precision, applicable to complex biological systems.	Infectious disease diagnostics.

3. Therapeutic Intervention Strategies

3.1. Targeted Gene Therapy

Targeted gene therapy represents a sophisticated molecular intervention strategy that harnesses advanced nanoscale technologies to revolutionize precision medicine. Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) nanotechnologies have emerged as a pivotal platform for developing sophisticated gene delivery mechanisms, enabling unprecedented control over genetic material transportation and cellular modulation. The intricate process involves strategically engineered nanoparticulate systems designed to navigate complex biological environments with remarkable specificity and efficiency. These nanoscale vectors are meticulously engineered to overcome traditional barriers associated with genetic material transmission, such as enzymatic degradation, immune system recognition, and cellular membrane penetration. By implementing sophisticated surface modifications and utilizing advanced molecular engineering techniques, researchers can now create nanoscale carriers capable of precise genetic material targeting and controlled release.

The fundamental architecture of these nanocarriers encompasses multifunctional components that facilitate enhanced cellular penetration while simultaneously minimizing potential off-target interactions. Sophisticated surface functionalization techniques allow for selective receptor-mediated

cellular uptake, ensuring that therapeutic genetic constructs are delivered exclusively to intended cellular populations. This molecular precision significantly reduces systemic toxicity and improves therapeutic efficacy by circumventing non-specific genetic material distribution. The nanoscale platforms leverage intricate molecular recognition mechanisms, incorporating ligands and peptide sequences that interact specifically with target cell surface receptors, thereby enabling highly selective genetic material internalization. Technological advancements in SPR nanotechnologies have substantially improved the molecular design of gene delivery systems, emphasizing controlled release kinetics and optimal genetic material integrity preservation. These innovative approaches integrate multiple strategic components, including protective molecular coatings, pH-responsive polymeric structures, and intelligent cargo-release mechanisms that respond dynamically to specific cellular microenvironments. The sophisticated engineering enables precise modulation of genetic material release rates, ensuring sustained and controlled therapeutic interventions. The molecular mechanisms underlying these targeted gene therapy approaches involve complex interactions between nanocarrier architectures and cellular environments. Researchers leverage advanced computational modeling and experimental validation to optimize nanoparticle surface properties, ensuring maximal therapeutic genetic material stability and

minimal immunological reactivity. The integration of molecular targeting strategies, such as ligand-mediated recognition and receptor-specific binding, represents a paradigm shift in genetic therapeutic interventions.

REFERENCE

- Chen, Y. (2023). *Surface Plasmon Resonance Imaging: Basic Theory and Practical Methodology* (Vol. 95). Springer Nature.
- Shen, G. Y., Chen, Y., Zhang, Y., & Cui, J. (2010). Surface Plasmon Resonance Imaging. *Progress in Chemistry*, 22(08), 1648.
- Phillips, K. S., & Cheng, Q. (2007). Recent advances in surface plasmon resonance based techniques for bioanalysis. *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*, 387, 1831-1840.
- Madhu, P. C. (2024). Chapter-11 Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR). ISBN: Book DOI: Price:839/-, 79, 197.
- Spoto, G., & Minunni, M. (2012). Surface plasmon resonance imaging: what next?. *The journal of physical chemistry letters*, 3(18), 2682-2691.
- Dai, J., & Fu, L. H. (2024). Denoising of Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) Spectra Using the Generalized S-transform and the Bald Eagle Search (BES) Algorithm. *Analytical Letters*, 57(11), 1778-1788.
- Maheshwari, R. U., Kumarganesh, S., KVM, S., Gopalakrishnan, A., Selvi, K., Paulchamy, B., ... & Pandey, D. (2024). Advanced plasmonic resonance-enhanced biosensor for comprehensive real-time detection and analysis of deepfake content. *Plasmonics*, 1-18.
- Burris, D. M., Gillespie, S. W., Campbell, E. J., Ice, S. N., Yadav, V., Picking, W. D., ... & Singh, K. (2024). Applications of Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) to the Study of Diverse Protein-Ligand Interactions. *Current Protocols*, 4(6), e1030.
- Swami, S., Kayenat, F., & Wajid, S. (2024). SPR biosensing: Cancer diagnosis and biomarkers quantification. *Microchemical Journal*, 197, 109792.
- Acharya, B., Behera, A., & Behera, S. (2024). Optimizing drug discovery: Surface plasmon resonance techniques and their multifaceted applications. *Chemical Physics Impact*, 8, 100414.
- Kant, K., Beeram, R., Cabaleiro, L. G., Cao, Y., Quesada-González, D., Guo, H., ... & Pastoriza-Santos, I. (2024). Roadmap for plasmonic nanoparticle sensors: Current progress, challenges and future prospects. *Nanoscale horizons*.
- Taha, B. A., Kadhim, A. C., Addie, A. J., Haider, A. J., Azzahrani, A. S., Raizada, P., ... & Arsad, N. (2024). Advancing cancer diagnostics through multifaceted optical biosensors supported by nanomaterials and artificial intelligence: A panoramic outlook. *Microchemical Journal*, 111307.
- Ramachandran, T., Ali, A., Butt, H., Zheng, L., Deader, F. A., & Rezeq, M. D. (2024). Gold on the horizon: unveiling the chemistry, applications and future prospects of 2D monolayers of gold nanoparticles (Au-NPs). *Nanoscale Advances*, 6(22), 5478-5510.
- Conte, R., Foggia, R., Valentino, A., Di Salle, A., Kandsi, F., & Calarco, A. (2024). Nanotechnology advancements transforming molecular diagnostics: Applications in precision healthcare. *International Journal of Nano Dimension*, 15(3).
- Hemdan, M., Ali, M. A., Doghish, A. S., Mageed, S. S. A., Elazab, I. M., Khalil, M. M., ... & Amin, A. S. (2024). Innovations in Biosensor Technologies for Healthcare Diagnostics and Therapeutic Drug Monitoring: Applications, Recent Progress, and Future Research Challenges. *Sensors* (Basel, Switzerland), 24(16), 5143.
- KVM, S., Pandey, B. K., & Pandey, D. (2024). Design of Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) Sensors for Highly Sensitive Biomolecular Detection in Cancer Diagnostics. *Plasmonics*, 1-13.
- Lien, D. (2024). The Role of DNA Nanotechnology in Medical Sensing. *Analytical Methods*.
- Polley, N., Gnanasekaran, B., & Umapathy, S. Nanotechnology in Biosensing: The Future of Disease Diagnosis. In *Applications of Nanotechnology in Biomedical Engineering* (pp. 85-110). CRC Press.

19. Idil, N., Aslyüce, S., & Mattiasson, B. (2024). Surface Plasmon Resonance Nanosensors for the Sensing of Bacterial Threats. In *Plasmonic Nanosensors for Biological and Chemical Threats* (pp. 142-176). CRC Press.
20. Putri, S. A., & Yulianto, B. (2024, February). Surface Plasmon Resonance Application for Bacteria Pathogen Detection: A Minireview. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2705, No. 1, p. 012022). IOP Publishing.
21. Chakraborty, A., Mitra, S., Chatterjee, M., Dey, A., & Mukherjee, S. (2024). Recent advancements in developing nanobiosensors for treating inflammatory diseases of human: a comprehensive overview. *Applications of Biotribology in Biomedical Systems*, 79-111.
22. Murugan, D., Tintelott, M., Narayanan, M. S., Vu, X. T., Kurkina, T., Rodriguez-Emmenegger, C., ... & Pachauri, V. (2024). Recent Advances in Grating Coupled Surface Plasmon Resonance Technology. *Advanced Optical Materials*, 12(34), 2401862.
23. Sumit, Gupta, S., & Kaushal, A. (2024). Advanced Diagnostic Techniques for Scrub Typhus: From Conventional Methods to Nanotechnology Solutions. *ChemistrySelect*, 9(34), e202402240.
24. Maleki, J., & Fathi, D. (2024). Refractive index sensor based on fano-magnetic toroidal quadrupole resonance enabled by bound state in the continuum in all-dielectric metasurface. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 4110.
25. Dixit, K. P. (2024). Design, Modeling, and Experimental Realization of Tunable Fabry-Perot Nanocavities for Broadband and Narrow-Band Applications. The University of Alabama in Huntsville.
26. Lu, C. (2017). Nano-DNA induced target assemblies-detection of small targets of DNA by forming networks (Doctoral dissertation, Université Grenoble Alpes).
27. Linman, M. J., & Cheng, Q. J. (2009). Surface plasmon resonance: new biointerface designs and high-throughput affinity screening. *Optical Guided-Wave Chemical and Biosensors I*, 133-153.
28. Ahmed, B., Elgorban, A. M., Bahkali, A. H., Lee, J., & Syed, A. (2022). SPR based gold nano-probe as optical sensor for cysteine detection via plasmonic enhancement in the presence of Cr³⁺. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 265, 120356.
29. Trojanowicz, M. (2023). Impact of nanotechnology on progress of flow methods in chemical analysis: A review. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 341643.
30. Zhuang, B., Yang, Y., Huang, K., & Yin, J. (2024). Plasmon-enhanced NIR-II photoluminescence of rare-earth oxide nanoprobe for high-sensitivity optical temperature sensing. *Optics Letters*, 49(22), 6489-6492.
31. Ranjbari, F., Nosrat, A., Fathi, F., & Mohammadzadeh, A. (2024). Surface plasmon resonance biosensors for early troponin detection. *Clinica Chimica Acta*, 118670.
32. Yesudasu, V., Pradhan, H. S., Pandya, R. J., Thiyaneswaran, B., Vanaja, S., Hossain, M. A., & Rashed, A. N. Z. (2024). Numerical investigation of Ag-franckeite-barium titanium-BP-based highly performed surface plasmon resonance sensor for virus SARS-CoV-2 detection. *Plasmonics*, 19(1), 167-178.
33. Zheng, J., Haseeb, A., Wang, Z., & Wang, H. (2024). Network pharmacology, computational biology integrated surface plasmon resonance technology reveals the mechanism of ellagic acid against rotavirus. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 7548.
34. Maheshwari, R. U., Paulchamy, B., Pandey, B. K., & Pandey, D. (2024). Enhancing sensing and imaging capabilities through surface plasmon resonance for deepfake image detection. *Plasmonics*, 1-20.
35. Nanda, B. P., Rani, P., Paul, P., & Bhatia, R. (2024). Recent Trends and Impact of Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance (LSPR) and Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) in Modern Analysis. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis*.
36. Goswami, A., Garg, S., Bhatt, E., Chaudhary, V., & Dang, S. (2024). Nanotechnology-Based Biosensors for Biomedical Applications. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 171(9), 097508.
37. Dhandapani, G., Wekalao, J., Patel, S. K., & Al-zahrani, F. A. (2024). Design and analysis of a highly sensitive terahertz biosensor using graphene metasurfaces and surface plasmon

- resonance for protein detection with AI-assisted locally weighted linear regression for behavior prediction. *Plasmonics*, 1-27.
38. Vasimalla, Y., Singh, S., Balaji, R., Srither, S. R., & Kumar, S. (2024). Detection of *Serratia marcescens* and *Micrococcus lysodeikticus* Bacterial Cells Using Cerium Oxide/Transition Metal Dichalcogenides Heterostructure-Based Surface Plasmon Resonance Sensor. *Advanced Photonics Research*, 2400136.
 39. Khitous, A., Lartigue, L., Moreau, J., & Soppera, O. (2024). Insights into Photopolymerization at the Nanoscale Using Surface Plasmon Resonance Imaging. *Small*, 20(40), 2401885.
 40. Alsaif, H., Wekalao, J., Ali, N. B., Kahouli, O., Logeshwaran, J., Patel, S. K., & Armghan, A. (2024). Design and optimization of a MXene-based terahertz surface plasmon resonance sensor for malaria detection. *Plasmonics*, 1-11.
 41. Zhou, J., Wang, Y., & Zhang, G. J. (2024). State-of-the-art strategies of surface plasmon resonance biosensors in clinical analysis: A comprehensive review. *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, 520, 216149.
 42. D'Agata, R., Bellassai, N., & Spoto, G. (2024). Exploiting the design of surface plasmon resonance interfaces for better diagnostics: A perspective review. *Talanta*, 266, 125033.
 43. Kant, K., Beeram, R., Cabaleiro, L. G., Cao, Y., Quesada-González, D., Guo, H., ... & Pastoriza-Santos, I. (2024). Roadmap for plasmonic nanoparticle sensors: Current progress, challenges and future prospects. *Nanoscale horizons*.
 44. Wekalao, J., U, A. K., Almawgani, A. H., Abdelrahman Ali, Y. A., Manvani, R., & Patel, S. K. (2024). Graphene-based THz surface plasmon resonance biosensor for hemoglobin detection applicable in forensic science. *Plasmonics*, 19(4), 2141-2154.
 45. Giarola, J. F., Estevez, M. C., & Lechuga, L. M. (2024). Plasmonic biosensors: Towards fully operative detection platforms for biomedical application and its potential for the diagnosis of autoimmune diseases. *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 117763.
 46. Bouhenna, A., Zeggai, O., Wekalao, J., Achour, A., & Mouloudj, H. (2024). High-performance terahertz surface plasmon resonance sensor with graphene-perovskite metasurface for early cancer detection. *Plasmonics*, 1-14.
 47. Ansari, A., Siddique, M. U. M., Nayak, A. K., Askari, V. R., Zairov, R. R., Aminabhavi, T. M., & Hasnain, M. S. (2025). Biosensors: History and classifications. In *Fundamentals of Biosensors in Healthcare* (pp. 1-20). Academic Press.
 48. Wekalao, J., Mandela, N., Langat, W., & wamalwa, C. (2024). Enhanced fuel adulteration detection using surface plasmon resonance biosensor with machine learning optimization in the terahertz regime. *Plasmonics*, 1-25.
 49. Akouibaa, A., Akouibaa, A., Masrour, R., Benhamou, M., Rezzouk, A., & Heryanto, H. (2024). Numerical simulation of early detection of cancer cells using a D-shaped fiber-optic biosensor based on surface plasmon resonance. *Journal of Cluster Science*, 35(7), 2459-2474.
 50. Kumar, R., Shah, R. S., Alsubaie, A. S., Ali, N. B., Kumar, M., & Pal, A. (2024). Hafnium diselenide 2D material-based surface plasmon resonance sensor for detection of basal cancer. *Plasmonics*, 1-10.

HOW TO CITE: Shashikant, Meghna Singh, Faith Ruth Dixon, Aniruddha Basak, Mahammad Ayaan, Arnab Roy, Illuminating the Future of Medicine: Surface Plasmon Resonance-Based Nanotechnologies for Genetic Disorder Management, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2024, 1 (12), 220-229. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14504308>